

Dissertation Summary

Active Galactic Nuclei at parsec scales

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Introduction

In this thesis we have performed a comprehensive investigation of the central few parsecs of nearby AGN, focused on two complementary aspects: *i*) **Characterization of the nuclear emission of low-luminosity AGN (LLAGN, $L_{\text{bol}} \lesssim 10^{42}$ erg/s) and comparison with the high-luminosity AGN**, and *ii*) **Characterization of spatially resolved star-forming regions located very close ($\lesssim 500$ pc) to the active nucleus**. We start from a multiwavelength and high spatial resolution dataset of a sample of six active galaxies: NGC 253, NGC 1097, NGC 1386, NGC 1052, NGC 7582, and NGC 7469 (sorted by increasing distance). This dataset includes the highest spatial resolution data available nowadays, covering a very wide range in wavelength: NIR adaptive optics images (VLT/NaCo), diffraction-limited imaging in the MIR (VLT/VISIR) and optical/UV (*HST*), radio maps from VLA mostly in A-configuration and VLBI/VLBA interferometry, and X-ray observations from *Chandra*. The result is a very consistent spatial resolution of a few tens of parsecs for the whole electromagnetic spectrum, which is precisely one of the biggest advantages when compared with previous studies.

Nuclear emission of LLAGN and comparison with high-luminosity AGN

LLAGN are by far the largest class of AGN and are found in $\gtrsim 50$ –70% of all galaxies (Ho, 2008). However, they represent a challenging scenario for AGN unification theories. Firstly, observations by Ho (1999) and Eracleous et al. (2010) suggest the absence in these objects of a big blue bump, i.e., the footprint of the accretion disk in the optical/UV range. LLAGN are therefore postulated as radiatively inefficient sources lacking the “standard” accretion disk. Secondly, the obscuring torus, a key element in unification models, is expected to vanish below $\lesssim 10^{42}$ erg/s, i.e., in the luminosity range inhabited by LLAGN (Elitzur & Shlosman, 2006; Hönic et al., 2006). Furthermore, the spatial resolution has a

critical impact for AGN below $\sim 10^{44}$ erg/s. In this case, nuclear SEDs based on photometry from apertures larger than $\sim 1''$ are in general dominated by the host galaxy contribution and not by the AGN, in contrast with those based on apertures of $\lesssim 0''.1$ (~ 8 pc in our sample), which are AGN-dominated (Prieto et al., 2010).

Within the sample of six galaxies, we distinguish four LLAGN: NGC 253, NGC 1097, NGC 1386, and NGC 1052. NGC 253 is the faintest one, the prototypical LINERs NGC 1097 and NGC 1052 are slightly more powerful, while NGC 1386 is a faint Seyfert 2. For these nuclei we built high spatial resolution SEDs and compared them with average SEDs for bright Seyferts (Prieto et al., 2010) and LINERs (Ho, 1999; Eracleous et al., 2010). The main conclusions from this comparison are:

i) The IR-to-optical SED of AGN with luminosities in the range 10^{42} – 10^{44} erg/s reflects the presence of a central obscuring structure, less than a few parsecs in size, in both type 1 and type 2 Seyferts, in agreement with the torus considered in unified schemes.

ii) SEDs of LLAGN with $\lesssim 10^{42}$ erg/s do not show signs of the presence of this structure. In contrast, they exhibit a gentle fall-off in the MIR to UV range. This fall is not as drastic as the characteristic one in bright Seyfert 2s (Sy2s) and cannot be reproduced by moderate reddening of a high-luminosity Seyfert 1 (Sy1).

iii) At radio wavelengths, LLAGN appear slightly different from the high-luminosity radio-quiet AGNs studied by us, but resemble what is seen in radio-loud quasars. These, such as Sy1s, show the characteristic blue bump in their spectra. In contrast, LLAGN do not, and this absence is not caused by dust extinction (this work). Thus, we favor the scenario in which LLAGN sustain a tenuous, radiatively inefficient disk or even lack this structure.

iv) We found a very bright X-ray source in the center of NGC 253 (called X-1), which

lacks optical, IR and radio counterparts (Müller-Sánchez et al., 2010). This suggests the presence of a strongly obscured AGN, whereas the rest of the spectrum indicates a starburst-dominated nuclei. The case of this galaxy is quite similar to that of NGC 4945, a well-known starburst galaxy with an AGN core detected only in the hard X-ray band ($L_{2-10\text{ keV}} \sim 10^{45}$ erg/s, Marconi et al., 2000). We believe that X-1 in NGC 253 is a low-luminosity ($L_{2-10\text{ keV}} \sim 10^{40}$ erg/s) member of the same class as NGC 4945. These “embedded AGN” are reminiscent of ultraluminous IR galaxies (ULIRGs) in the sense that the starburst component seems to be hiding or heavily obscuring the AGN.

Resolved star-forming regions close to an AGN

We have been able to resolve star-forming regions in the central parsecs of all the objects in the sample at different distances from the active nucleus. These take the form of starburst rings with diameters of about 1 kpc (NGC 1097, NGC 1386, NGC 7469), compact starburst disks within the inner $\lesssim 500$ pc (NGC 253, NGC 7582), or a random distribution within the central few kpc (NGC 1052). In each galaxy, and for each of the star-forming regions found, we obtained a multiwavelength SED and provide estimates for the age, mass, and size (Fernández-Ontiveros et al., in preparation). A comparative analysis of the properties of these regions is produced:

i) Most of the star-forming regions appear to be very homogeneous regardless of the galaxy type or AGN luminosity, with similar SEDs, very compact sizes (3–20 pc, in most cases still limited by the achieved spatial resolution), and ages in the 3–20 Myr range. These properties are similar to those of young stellar clusters (YSCs) found in the Milky Way (10^3 – $10^4 M_{\odot}$, as well as in NGC 1386 and NGC 1052), starbursts and interacting galaxies ($\gtrsim 10^4 M_{\odot}$, in the remaining objects; Mengel et al., 2005; Portegies Zwart et al., 2010).

ii) NGC 253 is a special case because of its proximity (~ 4 Mpc), which allows us to compile the most complete SED for most of its nuclear star-forming regions from the UV to the radio down to scales of ~ 3 pc (Fernández-Ontiveros et al., 2009). A characteristic IR bump ($1\text{--}2\ \mu\text{m}$), seen in most of the SEDs for the YSCs in the nucleus of this galaxy, is identified as the signature of very young protostellar objects being currently produced in these clusters.

iii) The cluster mass function (CMF) for NGC 253 – the youngest system with 4.3 Myr old in average – follows a power law with an index of $\gamma \approx 1.8$, close to the common behavior of many diverse star-forming systems ($\gamma \approx 2$, Portegies Zwart et al., 2010). NGC 7469 shows a steeper CMF with $\gamma \approx 3.5$, more similar to very massive star-forming clusters ($\gtrsim 10^6 M_\odot$). However, in this case we suspect that the clusters are not individually resolved.

iv) A truncated CMF is found in NGC 1097, which is very well fitted by a Schechter profile with a characteristic mass of $M_* \sim 2.1 \times 10^5 M_\odot$. Since this is the oldest system with 10 Myr old on average, a possible explanation for this truncation is the internal dynamical evolution favoring the disruption of the less massive clusters (Fall & Zhang, 2001).

v) We found 25 compact clusters ($\lesssim 11$ pc) in the central 2×2 kpc² of the elliptical NGC 1052 (Fernández-Ontiveros et al., 2010). Their location around the nucleus is sparse and does not correlate with the distribution of the radio lobes, H I, ionized gas or dust. Of these clusters, at least 15 present strong H α emission ($L_{\text{H}\alpha} \sim 3.8 \times 10^{36}$ erg/s). The possible contribution of an old population to the UV continuum, via extreme horizontal branch stars, cannot account for the H α luminosity. In contrast, cluster SEDs and $L_{\text{H}\alpha}$ values can be explained in terms of a very young population (~ 6 Myr, or ~ 12 Myr for the lowest metallicity case) with masses of about $10^4 M_\odot$ and extinction values of $A_V \sim 3.4$ mag. Thus, we propose that these are YSCs formed in a very recent star-formation episode, probably related with a merger event suffered by this galaxy ~ 1 Gyr ago (van Gorkom et al., 1986).

References

- Elitzur, M., & Shlosman, I. 2006, *ApJ*, 648, L101
- Eracleous, M., Hwang, J. A., & Flohic, H. M. L. G. 2010, *ApJS*, 187, 135
- Fall, S. M., & Zhang, Q. 2001, *ApJ*, 561, 751
- Fernández-Ontiveros, J. A., López-Sanjuan, C., Montes, M., Prieto, M. A., & Acosta-Pulido, J. A. 2010, ArXiv e-prints
- Fernández-Ontiveros, J. A., Prieto, M. A., & Acosta-Pulido, J. A. 2009, *MNRAS*, 392, L16
- Ho, L. C. 1999, *ApJ*, 516, 672
- . 2008, *ARA&A*, 46, 475
- Hönig, S. F., Beckert, T., Ohnaka, K., & Weigelt, G. 2006, *A&A*, 452, 459
- Marconi, A., Oliva, E., van der Werf, P. P., Maiolino, R., Schreier, E. J., Macchetto, F., & Moorwood, A. F. M. 2000, *A&A*, 357, 24
- Mengel, S., Lehnert, M. D., Thatte, N., & Genzel, R. 2005, *A&A*, 443, 41
- Müller-Sánchez, F., González-Martín, O., Fernández-Ontiveros, J. A., Acosta-Pulido, J. A., & Prieto, M. A. 2010, *ApJ*, 716, 1166
- Portegies Zwart, S. F., McMillan, S. L. W., & Gieles, M. 2010, *ARA&A*, 48, 431
- Prieto, M. A., Reunanen, J., Tristram, K. R. W., Neumayer, N., Fernandez-Ontiveros, J. A., Orienti, M., & Meisenheimer, K. 2010, *MNRAS*, 402, 724
- van Gorkom, J. H., Knapp, G. R., Raimond, E., Faber, S. M., & Gallagher, J. S. 1986, *AJ*, 91, 791